

Teaching Preference Among Saudi Medical Students In Tabuk City

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Abstract

Problem based learning (PBL), team-based pedagogy (TBL), and flipped classes are increasingly incorporated replacing traditional lectures in medical teaching to improve reasoning and information retention. No researchers have compared PBL, TBL, and flipped classes with traditional lectures in Tabuk, Saudi Arabia. The study aimed to assess the same among medical students. This cross-sectional study was conducted among 246 Medical students in the Faculty of Medicine, University of Tabuk during March and April 2023. A web-based questionnaire was used to collect the information. The student's preference regarding traditional classroom, TBL, PBL, and the flipped classroom was tested by inquiring about which type of classes improves their cumulative grade average and helps them to retain information. In addition, the student's preparation and accountability towards TBL and flipped classes was tested. There were 246 medical students (58.6% females), 63.8% thought that traditional lectures helped them to retain information, followed by TBL (14.2%), PBL (13.0%), while only 8.9% believed that flipped classes did so. Regarding the cumulative grade average, 64.6% of the students thought that traditional lectures are more helpful, followed by PBL, TBL, and flipped classes, in 12.6%, 11.8%, and 11% respectively. The student's preparation, accountability, and attitude towards team-based learning and flipped classes was poor (preparation score ranged from 5.42 -5.61 out of 10, and accountability ranged from 4.96 -5.14). Students prefer traditional lectures to new learning methods. Their preparation and accountability were poor for TBL and flipped classes. Larger studies assessing the barriers to the new learning methods are needed.

Introduction

Traditional lecture modality could not fulfill the need of modern medicine and is less effective than other teaching strategies in high-order learning abilities. The flipped classroom has shifted the teacher-centered passive instructional strategies to student-centered active processes (Prober and Heath 2012), Chen, 2018. Reversing the traditional lectures by giving the students faculty-provided instructional content to review outside the classroom and take part in face-to-face interactive learning based on their preparatory work under the instructor's guidance in the classroom (Tucker, (2012)). Flipped class education showed a positive impact on academic performance in basic and clinical education, and has been extended to involve residency programs and board teaching (Persky and McLaughlin, 2017, Ge, 2020, Chen, 2017, Ramnanan and Pound, 2017, Burgess, 2017).

Team-based learning (TBL) has the advantage over problem-based learning (PBL) due to the smaller groups and fewer tutors needed. In addition, TBL showed more student engagement and participation (Burgess, 2018).

Both TBL and PBL rely on constructivist learning theory to engage and motivate students in their learning. However, differences exist between PBL and TBL in terms of preparation requirements, group numbers, learning strategies, and class structure (Liu, 2020, Poeppelman, 2016). Executive, financial, and technical barriers were reported in the implementation of TBL. Team-based learning appears to be effective in graduate medical education with learner reactions ranging from positive to neutral (Shen, 2022). Recent studies showed that TBL could be incorporated into flipped classes with positive effects on academic achievement (Rezende, 2020). Results of randomized controlled trials regarding the superiority of TBL over traditional lectures contradicting (Alamoudi, 2021, Thrall, 2016, Kazory and Zaidi, 2018).

The Faculty of Medicine adopted a six-year curriculum with mixed traditional lectures, flipped classes, team-based learning, and problem-based learning. To the best of my knowledge, no researchers have assessed the teaching preference among medical students in Tabuk. In this study, we aim to explore the learning approach and teaching preference among medical students, at the University of Tabuk, Saudi Arabia.

Subjects and Methods:

This cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted among 246 Medical students in the Faculty of Medicine, University of Tabuk. The study was conducted during March and April 2023. A web-based questionnaire was used to collect the information. The student list was taken from the Vice Dean of Academic Affairs and every second student was chosen, then the questionnaire was distributed through e-mails. The participant's consent was included in the questionnaire and when the student chooses not to agree the questionnaire will close. The purpose of the survey was explained to the participants. After dropping out of 20%, the sample size will be increased to 246 students.

Measures:

The student's preference regarding traditional classroom, team-based learning (TBL), problem-based learning (PBL), and the flipped classroom was tested by inquiring about which type of classes improves their cumulative grade average and helps them to retain information (Poepelman, 2016). In addition, the student's preparation and accountability towards TBL and flipped classes were tested using a ten-point Likert scale.

Ethical issues:

The ethical committee of the University of Tabuk will approve the research (ref. UT-279-122-2023, dated, 6/4/2023). The participant's consent was taken before responding to the questionnaire.

Statistical analysis

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, version, 20, New York) was used for data analysis. The ethical committee of the University of Tabuk will approve the research.

Results:

There were 246 medical students (58.6% females), 35.7% were third class, 17.2% second class, and 17.6%, 16%, 6.1%, and 7.4% were from the fifth, sixth, first, and fourth classes respectively. Table 1.

In the present study, nearly two-thirds of medical students (63.8%) thought that traditional lectures helped them to retain information, followed by team-based learning 14.2%, and problem-based learning 13.0%, while only 8.9% believed that flipped classes did so. Regarding the cumulative grade average, 64.6% of the students thought that traditional lectures are more helpful, followed by problem-based learning, team-based learning, and flipped classes, in 12.6%, 11.8%, and 11% respectively. Table 2. It is interesting to note that the student's attitude towards team-based learning and flipped classes was poor. The scores were 4.96 out of ten in preparation for flipped classes, and 5.14 out of 10 in preparing for team-based learning. While they scored 5.61 out of 10 in their accountability towards team-based learning, and 5.42 out of ten in their accountability for flipped classes. Table 3.

Table 1. Deep motive among medical students at the University of Tabuk, Saudi Arabia

Character	No %
Sex	
Females	143 (58.6%)
Males	101 (41.4%)
Class	
First-year	15 (06.1%)
Second year	42 (17.2%)
Third year	87 (35.7%)
Fourth-year	18 (07.4%)
Fifth year	43 (17.6%)
Six year	39 (16.0%)

Table 2. The student's perception of different types of classes.

Character	No %
Which of the learning style helped you to retain information?	
Traditional lectures	157 (63.8%)
Team-based learning	35 (14.2%)
Problem-based learning	32 (13.0%)
Flipped classes	22 (8.9%)
Which of the learning style helped you to improve your GPA?	
Traditional lectures	159 (64.6%)
Team-based learning	29 (11.8%)
Problem-based learning	31 (12.6%)

Flipped classes	27 (11.0%)
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Table 3. The student's attitude toward team-based learning and flipped classes

Character	No %
Rate your preparation before team-based learning	5.14
Rate your preparation before flipped class	4.96
Please rate your accountability towards team-based learning	5.61
Please rate your accountability towards flipped class	5.42

Discussion

Problem-based learning (PBL) is an instructional supervised small group discussion of a problem; it is increasingly adopted in many medical schools worldwide. The advantages of PBL are knowledge retention through improving the problem-solving strategy. Problem-based learning enhances the integration of basic knowledge and clinical skills among medical students (Yaqinuddin, 2013, Bin Abdurrahman, 2008). The current findings indicated poor satisfaction with problem-based learning in our College, only 13% of medical students thought that PBL helped them retain information and 12.6% thought that PBL improved their cumulative grade average (GPA). The present findings contradicted previous studies conducted in similar settings in Saudi Arabia and found good satisfaction (AlHaqwi, 2008, Shamsan and Sayed, 2009). Obstacles to PBL should be explored in this Faculty to encourage this important teaching method, PBL improves discussion and student development, in addition, initiating discussion improved learning reasoning strategy and help knowledge sharing between groups (Dolmans, 1993, Hmelo-Silver, 2004). The relevance and applicability of PBL in this college need further exploration to set objectives according to the common health problems in this area to improve the learning outcomes. In the present data, the situation of team-based learning is alarming, only 14.2% and 11.8% of the students believed that team-based learning helped them in retaining knowledge and improving their GPA, and TBL was shown to improve the student's skills and competencies. Team-based learning pedagogy is increasingly incorporated, it is similar to PBL in reasoning but the groups are larger and needs fewer faculties, TBL is suitable for the clinical phase students who are already prepared by PBL in the foundation year (Abdelkhalek, 2010, Alamoudi, 2021). Our findings are not in line with previous studies that showed a good perception of TBL (Haidet and Fecile, 2006, Obad, 2016). A study conducted among Dentistry students showed a positive attitude towards TBL and PBL in contradiction to our findings (Nawabi, 2021). Flipped classes are inverted blended classes in which traditional lectures and homework are reversed, flipped classes enhance active learning, reduce passivity, and increase students' peers and instructors interaction (Rotellar and Cain, 2016). Studies comparing traditional lectures and flipped classes showed mixed results, some showed flipped classes preference (Abdulghani, 2022), while others showed diverse results compared to traditional classrooms (Alnahdi, 2022). In the present study, the students preferred traditional lectures to TBL, PBL, and flipped classes. Previous researchers showed that flipped classes are better in specific specialties including applied Science and Family Medicine (Howard, 2017). Barriers to flipped classrooms might be time constraints, lack of a genuine interest in the objectives, students' resistance to the new model, and lack of training for both the students and faculty members (Chen, 2014, Strayer, 2012, Gianoni-Capenakas, 2019). Students and faculty preparation for the new methods of teaching is urgently needed.

The study limitations were many: first, the reliance on a self-reported questionnaire, which is more prone to subjectivity, second, the study, was conducted at a single College, and thirdly, the small sample size.

Conclusion: The student's perception of problem-based, team-based, and flipped classes was poor; the students prefer traditional lectures over other methods of teaching. Further studies focus on barriers to the new methods of teaching.

Conflicts of interest: None to declare.

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